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A new antlion genus and species (Neuroptera: Myrmeleontidae) from the mid-Cretaceous Kachin amber of Myanmar

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Abstract: A new genus and species of the lacewing family Myrmeleontidae, *Babinoleon jinmingae* **gen. et sp. nov.**, is reported based on an adult specimen from the mid-Cretaceous Kachin amber of Myanmar. The new genus is characterized by the combination of the presence of two presectoral crossveins in both fore- and hind wings, the multi-bifurcated forewing CuA2, the long CuP+A1, the simple A2 and bifurcated A3, and the long and pectinately branched hind wing CuA. The morphological highlights and its phylogenetic implications are discussed.

Key words: Cretaceous, Kachin amber, Myrmeleontidae, new genus.

INTRODUCTION

Myrmeleontidae (antlions and owlflies) is the most species-rich family of Neuroptera, with over 2100 extant species distributed worldwide. The origin of Myrmeleontidae dates back to the Lower Cretaceous based on the oldest fossil records known to date, i.e., *Choromyrmeleon othneius* REN & GUO, 1996, while a Middle to Upper Jurassic origin was estimated based

on the molecular dating (WANG *et al.* 2017, WINTERTON *et al.* 2018, VASILIKOPOULOS *et al.* 2020). The monophyly of Myrmeleontidae is supported by the strongly dilated antennae, the origin of RP+MA slightly distal to wing base, and the presence of prolonged tibial spur, though the phylogenetic status of some Cretaceous species still needs further exploration (LU *et al.* 2019, 2021, 2022).

Hitherto, 54 fossil species in 30 genera of Myrmeleontidae have been recorded, spanning from the Lower Cretaceous to the Miocene (OSWALD 2025, see supplementary table1 in LU *et al.* 2019, LU & LIU 2021, table 1 in LU & LIU 2022, BUENO *et al.* 2026). The fossil records of Myrmeleontidae are overwhelmingly from the Mesozoic, accounting for the majority of known species. These are primarily from the Lower Cretaceous of Brazil (31 species; MARTINS-NETO & VULCANO 1989a,b, MARTINS-NETO 1992a,b, 1994, [2003] 2002, MARTINS-NETO & VULCANO 1997, MAKARKIN *et al.* 2018), with additional records from the mid-Cretaceous of Myanmar (7 species; HUANG *et al.* 2016, LU *et al.* 2019, YANG *et al.* 2020, LU & LIU 2022) and the Lower Cretaceous of China and Mongolia (3 species; PONOMARENKO 1992, REN & GUO 1996, REN & ENGEL 2008). The Cenozoic record is far less abundant, comprising the remaining 23 species from various localities in Europe and the Americas (see details in LU & LIU 2022). Besides, two species are described based solely on larval specimens from the Baltic and Kachin amber (MACLEOD 1971, BADANO *et al.* 2018).

Currently, seven antlion species described based on adults have been recorded from the mid-Cretaceous of Myanmar. Among them, four species that are characterized by the leaf-like forewing belong to the extinct subfamily Araripeneurinae (LU *et al.* 2019, YANG *et al.* 2020), while the remaining three species, i.e., *Burmanaura minuta* HUANG *et al.*, 2016, *Nanoleon wangae* HU, LU & LIU in LU *et al.*, 2019, *Xiaoleon amoena* LU & LIU, 2022 appear to be close to the extinct family Pseudonymphinae (HUANG *et al.* 2016, LU *et al.* 2019, LU & LIU 2021, 2022). Among the latter three antlions, only *N. wangae* possesses a presectoral crossvein in both fore- and hind wings, but it is developed broadly in extant antlions and Cenozoic fossil antlions.

Here we described a new genus and species of Myrmeleontidae, namely *Babinoleon jinmingae* **gen. et sp. nov.**, based on an adult specimen from the mid-Cretaceous Kachin amber of Myanmar. This new genus is remarkable by the presence of two presectoral crossveins in both fore- and hind wings, the multi-bifurcated forewing CuA2, the long forewing CuP+A1, the simple forewing A2 and bifurcated A3, and the long and pectinately branched hind wing CuA, the combination of which is unique in Myrmeleontidae. The present finding provides new evidence for the understanding of the diversity of Myrmeleontidae from the Cretaceous. The phylogenetic position of this new genus is also discussed.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The amber specimen herein described is from Hukawng Valley, Tanai Township, Myitkyina District, Kachin State, northern Myanmar (see KANIA *et al.* 2015: fig. 1), 26° 30' 0" N 96° 34' 59" E (Mindat.org 2025). The age of this deposit is dated to be ~98.8 Ma (the earliest Cenomanian) by U-Pb dating of zircons from the volcanoclastic matrix of the amber (SHI *et al.* 2012).

The holotype specimen is deposited in the Xiachong Amber Museum (XAM), Beijing, China. Photographs and drawings are prepared and made with a Leica TL5000 Ergo stereomicroscope connecting with a Nikon D850 digital camera system. The plates are

prepared with Adobe Photoshop CC 2019. Terminology of wing venation generally followed ASPÖCK *et al.* (1980) and KUKALOVÁ-PECK & LAWRENCE (2004).

Abbreviations used for wing venations are: A, anal vein; C, costa; Cu, cubitus; CuA, cubitus anterior; MP, media posterior; R, radius; RA, radius anterior; RP, radius posterior; ScA, subcosta anterior; ScP, subcosta posterior; ps, presectoral crossvein; cbr, basal radial cell; cir, infra radial cell; hc, hypostigmal cell.

All taxonomic acts established in this paper have been registered in ZooBank, together with the electronic publication: [urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:C6B0B46C-17AB-4B5D-BFC5-9A99105BD287].

SYSTEMATIC PALAEOLOGY

Class Insecta LINNAEUS, 1758

Order Neuroptera LINNAEUS, 1758

Family Myrmeleontidae LATREILLE, 1802

Subfamily incertae sedis

***Babinoleon* gen. nov.**

Type species: *Babinoleon jinmingae* sp. nov.

(Figs 1–2)

<https://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:81681F20-F441-490C-B4E3-E9DA3835B76A>

Diagnosis. The new genus is characterized by the combination of the following characters: (1) forewing RP+MA diverging from R slightly distal to wing base [shared by *Burmanaura*, *Nanoleon*, *Pseudonymphes* MARTINS-NETO & VULCANO, 1989a, *Caririneura* MARTINS-NETO & VULCANO, 1989a, and some extant antlions; more close to wing base in the other Cretaceous myrmeleontids]; (2) two forewing presectoral (ps) crossveins present [one forewing ps crossvein in *Nanoleon*, zero or one to two ps crossveins in *Caririneura*, three or more ps crossveins in most myrmeleontids; absent in *Burmanaura*, most genera of Araripeneurinae and the genera of Pseudonymphinae]; (3) two hind wing ps present [one ps crossvein in *Nanoleon*, two to three or six ps crossveins present in *Caririneura*, six to seven ps crossveins in *Phylloleon* LU, WANG & LIU in LU *et al.*, 2019, and three or more in most extant myrmeleontids; absent in most genera of Araripeneurinae and the genera of Pseudonymphinae]; (4) base of forewing MP2 (oblique vein) not detected [shared by *Burmanaura*, *Nanoleon*, and a few araripeneurines; present in the other myrmeleontids]; (5) space between forewing MP1 and MP2+CuA1 broad [shared by most antlions; strongly narrowed in araripeneurines]; (6) initial branching point of forewing MP2+CuA1 distinctly distal to diverging point of RP+MA from R [slightly distad in *Burmanaura*, *Nanoleon*, *Choromyrmeleon* REN & GUO, 1996, and pseudonymphines, but almost at the same level in most araripeneurines; variously configured in extant myrmeleontids]; (7) forewing CuA2 short [shared by most myrmeleontids; long in the genera of Araripeneurinae]; (8) forewing CuA2 bifurcated [shared by most myrmeleontids; simple in *Burmanaura* and *Cratoneura* MARTINS-NETO, 1992a; pectinately branched in the genera of Pseudonymphinae]; (9) hind

wing CuA terminating distal to diverging point of RP+MA from R, with at least four pectinate branches [shared by most myrmeleontids, but with more pectinate branches; hind wing CuA terminating proximal to diverging point of RP+MA from R in *Burmaneura*, *Caririneura*, *Porrerus* NAVÁS, 1913 and *Myrmeleon* LINNAEUS, 1767, usually with less branches].

Etymology. From “Babin-” (From the family Babinskaiidae, for the resemblance of the new genus to Babinskaiidae by the possession of presectoral crossveins) and “leon” (Greek, meaning “lion”, a frequent suffix of the genus-group name of Myrmeleontidae). Gender: Feminine.

Remarks. The new genus is definitely placed within Myrmeleontidae based on the similar wing venations, such as the single MP1, the origin of RP+MA slightly distad wing base, and the non-pectinately branched MP2+CuA1. It appears to be closely related to *Burmaneura*, *Nanoleon* and *Xiaoleon*, all from the Kachin amber, by the forewing RP+MA diverging from R slightly distad wing base, the absence of forewing oblique vein, the broad space of MP1 and MP2+CuA1, the short forewing infra radial cell (cir), and the short CuA2 and CuP branches. However, the new genus could be easily distinguished from them by the presence of two presectoral crossveins in both fore- and hind wings, the initial branching point of forewing MP2+CuA1 distinctly distal to diverging point of RP+MA from R, the bifurcated forewing CuA2 with multiple branches, the bifurcated forewing A3 and the longer forewing CuP+A1 and hind wing CuA. In the other three genera, only *Nanoleon* possess the presectoral crossvein in both fore- and hind wing but with only one; the initial branching point of forewing MP2+CuA1 is close to diverging point of RP+MA from R; forewing A3 is simple; the forewing CuA2 is simple in *Burmaneura*, bifurcated but only with one fork in the other two genera; the forewing CuP+A1 and hind wing CuA is shorter.

***Babinoleon jinmingae* sp. nov.**

(Figs 1–2)

<https://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:81681F20-F441-490C-B4E3-E9DA3835B76A>

Diagnosis. Same as for the genus.

Description. Body length 13.32 mm; head 1.72 mm long and 2.88 mm wide; antenna length 7.5 mm; prothorax 1.25 mm long and 1.10 mm wide; mesothorax 1.67 mm long and 1.96 mm wide; metathorax 1.46 mm long and 1.77 mm wide; incompletely preserved right forewing 10.95 mm long and 3.51 mm wide; incompletely preserved right hind wing 9.95 mm long and 2.64 mm wide; partly preserved left forewing length 8.47 mm; partly preserved left hind wing length 4.68 mm; abdomen length 8.14 mm.

Head orthognathous. Compound eyes large, semi-globular; antenna apex not preserved; prothorax shorter and slightly narrower than head; mesothorax robust, metathorax almost as wide as mesothorax. Wings slender, transparent, and immaculate.

Forewing incompletely preserved. Costal space narrow, about 2.5 times as wide as subcostal space, slightly widened distad, with 15 costal crossveins, all of which are simple. ScA and humeral veinlet absent; subcostal crossveins absent in preserved part. Two presectoral crossveins present. Five crossveins present in RA space, three of them present proximad diverging point between RP and MA. RP+MA diverging from R slightly distad

Fig. 1. *Babinoleon jinmingae* gen. et sp. nov. Holotype: XAM-MYR-26001. **A** – habitus photograph, left lateral view; **B** – photograph of wings; **C** – photograph of forewings; **D** – photograph of left hind leg. Scale bar = 1.0 mm.

Fig. 2. *Babinoleon jinmingae* gen. et sp. nov. Holotype: XAM-MYR-26001. **A** – drawing of right forewing; **B** – drawing of right hind wing. Scale bar = 1.0 mm.

wing base; infra radial cell short. MP1 long, distally not preserved; base of MP2 (oblique vein) untraceable. CuA and CuP diverging near wing base; initial branching point of forewing MP2+CuA distinctly distal to diverging point of RP+MA from R; CuA2 bifurcated from midpoint with at least five branches. CuP+A1 pectinately branched at its proximal 2/5, with eight simple branches. A1 fused with CuP, without cup-a1 crossvein; A2 simple, connecting with A1 with a short crossvein; A3 with a marginal fork, slightly curved posteriad, connected each other by a short crossvein.

Hind wing with only wing base preserved and slightly narrowed. Costal space slightly narrower than that of forewing, with eight simple costal crossveins: subcostal crossveins absent. Two presectoral crossveins present. RP+MA diverging from R slightly distal to wing base; one crossveins preserved in RA space. MP1 and MP2 long and straight; six crossveins present between MP1 and MP2. CuA stem running almost parallel to posterior margin, pectinately branched into four simple branches: CuP and A1 fused together, A2 and A3 simple and short.

Legs relatively short and stout; femur and tibia with sparsely spaced long spinous setae, and two long tibial spurs, which are almost straight, but with slightly curved apex. Tarsus 5-segmented, tarsomere 1 long, longer than combination of tarsomeres 2–4, but slightly shorter than tarsomere 5; tarsomeres 2–4 quite short, tarsomere 2 slightly longer than tarsomere 3; tarsomere 3 and tarsomere 4 almost same in length; tarsomere 5 longest; a pair of pretarsal claws present, slightly curved distally; arolium absent.

Abdomen slenderly elongated, with genitalia not preserved.

Type material. Holotype: XAM-MYR-26001: Amber piece preserving a partly preserved adult of *Babinoleon jinmingae* **sp. nov.** It is polished in the form of a flattened rectangle cabochon, with length×width about 20.56×13.89 mm, height about 5.76 mm.

Etymology. The new species is dedicated to Mrs. Jinming Zhang, a good friend of the author Mr. De Zhuo.

DISCUSSION

Notable characteristics of the new genus

The most notable morphological characters of *Babinoleon* **gen. nov.** refer to the distal shift of the origin of RP+MA, and the presence of two presectoral crossveins in both fore- and hind wings. The origin of RP+MA is a key character to distinguish lacewing families of Myrmeleontoidea. The origin of RP+MA close to wing base is a plesiomorphic state that is present in Nymphidae and Palaeoleontidae (see Fig. 10 in LU *et al.* 2021). The origin of RP+MA distinctly distad wing base is assigned to be the autapomorphy of Babinskaiidae, and the presence of at least two presectoral crossveins in both fore- and hind wings is assigned to support the sister-group relationship between Babinskaiidae and Cratosmylidae in the phylogenetic analysis (LU *et al.* 2021, 2022). Actually, considering the presence of two or more presectoral crossveins in advanced lineages of Myrmeleontidae, this venational trait might have been evolved independently among several myrmeleontoid families. However, the presence of two or more presectoral crossveins is rarely found in Cretaceous Myrmeleontidae (MARTINS-NETO & VULCANO 1989a,b, MARTINS-NETO 1992a,b, 1994, [2003] 2002, PONOMARENKO 1992, REN & GUO 1996, MARTINS-NETO & VULCANO 1997, REN & ENGEL 2008, HUANG *et al.* 2016, MAKARKIN *et al.* 2018, LU *et al.* 2019, YANG *et*

al. 2020, LU & LIU 2022). Therefore, superficially, the new genus resembles the species of Babinskaiidae, regarding the weak development of presectoral crossveins in contemporaneous Myrmeleontidae. Before the present finding, *Nanoleon wangae* from the Cretaceous Kachin amber is the only known antlion species, which possesses one presectoral crossvein in both fore- and hind wings, among the Cretaceous Myrmeleontidae. Thus, the new genus highlights the morphological diversity regarding the wing characters in the Cretaceous antlions.

Phylogenetic implication of the new genus

The diversity of antlions from the Cretaceous Kachin amber is not as high as that of the Crato Formation of Brazil, with only seven genera and eight species described based on adult to date. Among them, three genera that are characterized by the leaf-like forewings belong to the extinct subfamily Araripeneurinae (LU *et al.* 2019, YANG *et al.* 2020), while the remaining four genera, i.e., *Burmaneuera*, *Nanoleon*, *Xiaoleon* and *Bainoleon* **gen. nov.**, appear to be closer to the extant Myrmeleontidae (LU *et al.* 2019, 2021, LU & LIU 2022). Although the new genus is incompletely preserved, preventing the observation of most autapomorphies that define Araripeneurinae (see in LU *et al.* 2019, 2021, 2022, LU & LIU 2022), it could be distinguished from this subfamily by several key characters. In Araripeneurinae, the proximal portion of costal space is strongly narrowed in genera with leaf-like forewings, the space between MP1 and MP2+CuA1 is narrowed (autapomorphy in LU *et al.* 2019, 2021, 2022), and the CuP branches are long. In addition, most genera of Araripeneurinae lack forewing presectoral crossveins except *Caririneura macrothoracica* MAKARKIN *et al.*, 2018. However, these characters are present in the new genus. In contrast, the new genus appears to be closely related to *Burmaneuera*, *Nanoleon* and *Xiaoleon* by the similar wing venations (see Remarks in Systematic palaeontology).

Species diversity of Myrmeleontidae and Babinskaiidae from Kachin amber

The species diversity of antlions from the Kachin amber is noticeably lower than that of Babinskaiidae, despite the two groups exhibiting broadly similar body plans. Both antlions and some babinskaiids possess predatory adaptations, including elongate legs equipped with spines, although the spines of babinskaiids tend to be weaker (LU *et al.* 2021, LU & LIU 2022). Some babinskaiids also show indications of an arboreal lifestyle by the presence of strongly dilated tarsomeres (MAKARKIN & STANICZEK 2019). Given their morphological similarity and potential overlap in ecological roles, it is possible that partial niche overlap or ecological competition occurred between these groups during the Cretaceous. Such interactions may have influenced their differential evolutionary trajectories: Babinskaiidae eventually became extinct, whereas antlions persisted and diversified into the extant Myrmeleontidae. Although direct evidence of ecological replacement is lacking, the contrasting fates of these two morphologically similar lacewing lineages raise the possibility that shifts in ecological opportunity or competitive balance contributed to the long-term success of antlions. Future work on more fossil discoveries, quantitative ecomorphological analyses and macroevolutionary modelling that integrates ecological and trait-dependent diversification patterns may show whether shifts in ecological opportunity or competitive balance facilitated the long-term success of antlions.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Xingyue Liu and Xiumei Lu raised the conceptualization. Fengrui Wang prepared the drawings, and photographs; Xiumei Lu prepared the plates. De Zhuo proposed the species name. Xiumei Lu and Xingyue Liu performed writing. All authors contributed to the discussion.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

We have included all data in the article.

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